

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FELEKE****FIRST NAME: SOLOMON****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

INTRODUCTION TO ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

EUCLID main aim is helping students to master the art of writing academic and professional papers, which is very crucial in my professional carrier as well as writing of high quality academic papers. Some of the most important domains of knowledge that I found out in this document was the basics of easy writing, plagiarism, Standard American English vs Standard British English, and writing style. As International Public Health Students, this course pack teaches me a basic principle of scientific writing which helps in organizing of ideas and convey technical and scientific information clearly and accurately for the intended audience.

2) BASICS OF ESSAY

On the basic essay writing section of the module, it has been brought to my attention that the basic steps in writing an essay, importance of starting the work early, analyzing then answering the essay questions/tasks, importance of researching topics, and how to draft and structure the essay. In page four of the course pack it was stated that in conclusion, we will restate the answer to the question raised and summarize the main points. The essay section of the document stated that write the introduction and conclusion after the body and take time to revise the first draft extensively and make sure the paragraphs are in a logical order. Referencing is vital in academic essays and it guards the writer against plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 2-5).

3) CITATION AND PLAGIARISM BASICS

Plagiarism has been defined as copying of words, thoughts, and ideas without giving credit to the author of that source of information. In the course pack, it is clearly written and gives emphasis that plagiarism is unethical and serious academic offence. So that, we can easily prevent plagiarism by citing the author or source of the information. Citation is a formal reference to the source of information used in your essay/research (EUCLID 2019, 9-13).

I have found out how to cite the source of information and type of citations in the course. There are two types of citations: in-text citations and list of works cited. In text citations, we need to put the authors name in parenthesis with the page number that the information came from. Quotations and paraphrases are some of the common methods we use in text citations (EUCLID 2019, 14-19).

I picked it up that quotations that are over four lines will not contain quotation marks instead, we indented and put separate paragraph. We need to use quotations only when there is especially strong language in the quote that emphasizes the meaning very well and an authority figure says something that can help you persuade the reader (EUCLID 2019, 20). One of the usual and most recommended approaches in scientific write up is paraphrases. Paraphrases are writing the information in our own words by taking the ideas and information from the author. It must be our own words with different style without affecting the accurate representation of the idea and cite it accordingly. There is also a time which does not need citation that is when the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas (EUCLID 2019, 30-31).

It was mentioned that in our response paper we need to use 1 citation and in midterm and final exam recommended to use 2 or 3 citations. It is also advised to write in formal academic styles, and sometimes, personal examples (EUCLID 2019, 38-39).

4) ACADEMIC WRITING STYLES GUIDE

EUCLID recommends the Chicago rule (Turabian) and American English writing styles. A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. On page 52 of the course it was explained that writing style goes beyond the use of grammar and punctuation and it comprises different aspects, to list some: preferred sentence lengths, font usage, spelling (UK v US English), use of abbreviations, voice preferences (active v passive), paragraph numbering and indentation, the use of headings and lists. The most important points mentioned several times in the course pack is to be consistent and coherent in our writing style and US/British English style preference.

American versus British English difference is well explained in the first period of the course. I am interested on this section of the course and I preferred one natural style

that can I use it consistently. American English is currently the dominant influence on British English due to population number and big economy in US, high magnitude of the higher education, publishing industry and media in US, and international political and economic position of the U.S (EUCLID 2019, 54). The basic difference between Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE) includes spelling, punctuation, abbreviation, forms of possession, verb conjugations, grammar, and writing of date and time.

I used the Vancouver writing style in my Master of Public Health study seven years ago. I am motivated to learn Chicago writing style as I am new to this style and recommended by EUCLID. It has been brought to my attention that the Chicago Manual of Style is focused on book publishing, so it has few instructions to offer for formatting papers. Turabian's Manual for Writers is the official guide to applying Chicago style to "term papers, theses, and dissertations," that is, final manuscript (EUCLID 2019, 71). In this section of the course, proper use of margins, fonts, indents, justification, spacing, and page numbers in Chicago manual of style are well explained. Furthermore, I have gained knowledge from the course on how to use abbreviations, capitalization, use of compound words, how to properly use italic and quotation marks, bibliography, endnotes and footnotes.

5) CONCLUSION

As a non-native speaker who has minimal exposure to writing guide during high school and tertiary education training program I have encountered many challenges in academic writing. Given that the International Academic Writing course will be helpful to attain the required academic writing skill for my Ph.D. study and professional carrier. The basics of essay writing, American vs British English, and writing style were well explained in this course pack. Overall, I understood that the academic essay writing needs advanced training, critical and creative thinking, and professional ethics. I am confident that the lessons I learned in this period will help me in the upcoming modules of this course as well as for overall study programs.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack for Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.